

HISTORICAL SCIENCES

POLITICAL AND MILITARY ACTIVITIES OF THE KHWARAZMSHAHS IN AZERBAIJAN

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the political and military activities of the Khwarazmshahs in Azerbaijan during the late twelfth and early thirteenth centuries, with particular emphasis on the campaigns and governance of Jalal al-Din Khwarazmshah. The study employs a historical-critical and contextual methodology based on primary medieval sources and relevant regional scholarship. Political and military developments are analyzed alongside administrative practices and their socio-economic impact on the local population.

The article situates Khwarazmshah expansion within the broader context of Seljuk fragmentation, regional feudal rivalry, and the Mongol threat, highlighting Azerbaijan's strategic significance during this transitional period. Special attention is given to key regions such as Tabriz and Nakhchivan, where Jalal al-Din attempted to establish a new political center following the collapse of Khwarazmshah authority in Central Asia.

The findings demonstrate that although Jalal al-Din's rule in Azerbaijan was short-lived, his military campaigns and administrative policies significantly affected the region's political stability and social structure, contributing to the conditions that facilitated subsequent Mongol domination. By adopting a region-centered perspective, this study offers a reassessment of Khwarazmshah rule in Azerbaijan and contributes to the historiography of medieval Caucasia on the eve of the Mongol invasions.

Keywords: Khwarazmshah Jalal al-Din, 13th century Azerbaijani history, Mongol invasions, Nakhchivan campaign, Feudal power, strategic position.

INTRODUCTION.

In the early thirteenth century (1200-1220), the Middle East and the South Caucasus were under the influence of complex political processes. As a result of the disintegration of the Great Seljuk Empire (1038-1157), which had held a dominant position in the region from the late eleventh to the mid-twelfth century, central authority weakened and political fragmentation emerged among local feudal states and dynasties. This situation rendered the Caucasus and the lands of Azerbaijan increasingly vulnerable to the influence and interventions of external powers. At that time, political authority in Azerbaijan was exercised by several states, including the Eldiguzid state (the Atabegs of Azerbaijan, 1146-1225), the Shirvanshah state (861-1538), and the Aghsunqurids of Maragha (1122-1227). By the late twelfth century, the increasingly powerful Georgian Kingdom, along with the Khwarazmian Empire, which sought to maintain its influence in the region, emerged as the principal rival forces contending for control over Azerbaijan. During the late twelfth and early thirteenth centuries, military campaigns by the Georgians, Mongols, and Khwarazmians were launched against Azerbaijan. The absence of a unified state structure and strong local authority in Azerbaijan contributed to the increased frequency and destructive impact of these invasions.

RELATIONS BETWEEN THE ATABEGS OF AZERBAIJAN AND THE KHWARAZMIANS.

During the reign of Atabeg Shams al-Din Eldiguz, relations between the Atabegs of Azerbaijan and the Khwarazmians were marked by tension. Following the death of Sultan Sanjar (1117-1157) in 1157, Il-Arslan Khwarazmshah (1156-1172) launched a campaign to seize Nishapur and placed the region under siege. The ruler of Nishapur, Mu'ayyid Ay-Aba, relied on Arslan Shah for assistance, particularly on Shams al-Din Eldiguz. In an effort to halt the Khwarazmshah's advance, Shams al-Din Eldiguz marched from Hamadan to Rayy and then to Bistam. However, the battle fought between the two sides ended without a decisive outcome. As a result of Mu'ayyid Ay-Aba's submission to Khwarazmshah authority, Nishapur was ultimately lost (3, p. 68; 12, p.534).

Hostile relations with the Khwarazmians during the time of Shams al-Din Eldiguz were transformed into amicable ties under Atabeg Muhammad Jahan Pahlavan (1175-1186). The correspondence exchanged between Muhammad Jahan Pahlavan and Ala al-Din Tekish (1172-1200) was conducted in a spirit of friendship. In the first, second, and fourth letters, the parties discussed the establishment of diplomatic missions, the Khwarazmshah's desire to meet in person, and the exchange of gifts. In the third letter, however, they complained about the great distance between their realms and the resulting difficulty in maintaining frequent correspondence (3, p.78; 10, p.109).

Following the death of Qizil Arslan (1186-1191), the internal struggle for power within the Atabegs of Azerbaijan was exploited by Tughril III, who, after being released from captivity, seized control of Iraqi Iran. In his struggle against Tughril III, Qutluq Inanch sought assistance from Khwarazmshah Tekish. At the same time, the Abbasid caliph al-Nasir also wrote to Khwarazmshah Tekish, inviting him to the region to oppose Tughril III. After Tughril III was defeated, Hamadan and Iraqi Iran came under Khwarazmian rule. Shortly thereafter, Khwarazmshah Tekish sent a letter to Abu Bakr (1191-1210), proposing to grant him authority over Iraq and inviting him to a meeting. However, taking into account the Georgian incursions, Abu Bakr sent his brother Uzbek (1210-1225) to meet the Khwarazmshah instead (3, p.110). In 602 AH (1205-1206), Taj al-Din Ali Shah, the son of the Khwarazmshah, launched an attack on the territory of the Atabegs of Azerbaijan. In the ensuing battle, Abu Bakr emerged victorious and destroyed the fortress of Haydariyya (3, p.118). Thus, the friendly relations that had begun during the reign of Muhammad Jahan Pahlavan eventually gave way to hostility.

In the thirteenth century, the Mongol state strengthened in Central Asia, prompting the Khwarazmians to advance westward. The Khwarazmian attacks on the Eldiguzid state further exacerbated the situation. Initially, the attack was led by Ghiyath al-Din Pirshah, the son of Khwarazmshah Muhammad (1200-1220). In order to avert this campaign, Uzbek married his sister Jalaliyya to Pirshah (15, p.99). After Ghiyath al-Din Pirshah withdrew from Azerbaijan, Uzbek attempted to take advantage of the temporary stabilization by launching an attack against Iraq. Simultaneously, the Atabeg of Fars, Sa'd ibn Zangi (1194-1226), also advanced into Iraq. Upon learning of these attacks, Khwarazmshah Muhammad initiated a campaign and, within a short period, defeated Sa'd ibn

Zangi and took him captive. Khwarazmshah Muhammad then dispatched his vizier, Nasr al-Din Dawlatyar, to Uzbek, demanding his submission. Realizing that he lacked the strength to resist the Khwarazmshah, Uzbek ordered the khutba to be read in his name. Since Uzbek's principal fortresses and treasury fell into Khwarazmian hands, no tribute was demanded. During these years, the Georgians were once again preparing to launch a campaign against Azerbaijan. Atabeg Uzbek appealed to the Khwarazmshah for assistance, and as a result, the Georgian expedition did not materialize (11, p.30; 9, p. 366; 12, p.549).

The Khwarazmian state reached its greatest territorial extent during the reign of Ala al-Din Muhammad (1200-1220), transforming into a major political power stretching from the Caspian Sea to the Indian Ocean. However, this period was also marked by severe crises in the internal administration of the state. The tension that began with the killing of Mongol envoys in 1218 ultimately drew the Khwarazmians into open warfare with the Mongols. Between 1219 and 1221, the armies of Chinggis Khan inflicted devastating blows on the Khwarazmian state, bringing it to the brink of collapse. As a result, the main pillars of the state were destroyed, the capital Urgench and other major cities were devastated, and the foundations of political authority were severely undermined. The political vacuum created by the Mongol invasions (1219-1223) had particularly significant consequences for Azerbaijan. In the early 1220s, the commanders of Chinggis Khan advanced into the South Caucasus, entering the regions of Shirvan, Arran, and Nakhchivan. These campaigns further heightened Mongol interest in Azerbaijan due to its strategic and geographical position—situated at the crossroads of major trade routes and endowed with rich economic resources. In 1221, Mongol forces conducted military operations in the directions of Nakhchivan, Ganja, and Tbilisi, seeking to establish control over the region (2, p.163; 15, p. 99; 4, p. 38; 6, p. 92). Consequently, in the

early thirteenth century, the lands of Azerbaijan became a major arena of the Khwarazmian-Mongol confrontation.

KHWARAZMSHAH JALAL AL-DĪN'S CAMPAIGNS IN AZERBAIJAN.

In 1220, Ala al-Din Muhammad, ruler of the Khwarazmian state, died on the island of Abaskun in the Caspian Sea (located in present-day Gorgan, Iran). Following his death, the state found itself in a grave military and political crisis, as the Mongol armies of Chinggis Khan had devastated Khwarazmian territories through successive campaigns between 1219 and 1221. Shortly before his death, Khwarazmshah Muhammad had designated his son Jalal al-Din as his heir (12, p. 641; 7, p. 400). Unlike his father's weakened authority, Jalal al-Din sought to consolidate the remaining forces of the state and organize resistance against the Mongol invasion.

In the early years of his rule, Khwarazmshah Jalal al-Din waged a determined struggle against the Mongols. In November 1221, he inflicted a significant defeat on Chinggis Khan's forces at the Battle of Parwan around the Indus River. However, later in 1221, as a result of renewed and powerful Mongol offensives, he suffered defeat and was forced to retreat to India. In 1224, Jalal al-Din returned from India and launched a new campaign toward the lands of Iran and Azerbaijan (14, p. 249). His principal objective was to organize sustained resistance against the Mongols and to revive his state.

Jalal al-Din's plans concerning the Caucasus and Azerbaijan were of a strategic nature. In 1225, he entered Azerbaijan and captured Tabriz; in 1226, he launched a campaign against Georgia and seized Tbilisi, attempting to consolidate his position in the region. Nakhchivan and its surrounding areas were of particular importance to him, as the region was advantageous from a defensive standpoint and represented a strategic base for resistance against the Mongols. Between 1225 and 1230, Jalal al-Din sought to transform Azerbaijan into one of the main pillars of his rule while simultaneously confronting the Mongol threat and engaging in struggles with local feudal powers. After 1221, as a result of continuous Mongol attacks, Khwarazmshah Jalal al-Din was deprived of the principal centers of his state and, upon returning from India in 1224, began searching for a new base of consolidation. Since the Mongol danger remained acute, he was compelled to select a strategically advantageous territory in order to preserve his political and military position. Azerbaijan proved to be the most suitable region for this purpose, as the Mongol campaigns of 1220-1222 had disrupted political stability and deepened fragmentation among local feudal elites (14, p.99; 16, p. 49). In such circumstances, Jalal al-Din entered Azerbaijan with the aim of establishing a new center of authority and securing a base for resistance against the Mongols.

The economic and military significance of Azerbaijan was also one of the principal reasons behind the campaign. Cities such as Tabriz, Ganja, and Nakhchivan-located along major international trade routes running from north to south and from east to west-pos-

sessed substantial financial resources as well as strategically important military positions. When Jalal al-Din launched his campaign into Azerbaijan in 1225, one of his primary objectives was to bring these cities under his control. At the same time, another crucial strategic goal was to establish alliances among local feudal lords against the Mongol threat and to subordinate their military forces to his authority. In mid-1225, Jalal al-Din entered Tabriz with his army and from there directed his forces toward Nakhchivan. In Nakhchivan, the Khwarazmshah's army encountered various military and political actors. At that time, the administration of Nakhchivan was in the hands of Khatun Jalaliyya. First and foremost, local feudal rulers in the region sought to preserve their own positions and therefore approached Jalal al-Din's campaign with caution. Moreover, the continued Mongol threat, along with the territorial ambitions of the Georgian kingdom in the Caucasus, further complicated Jalal al-Din's military operations. As a result of the campaigns conducted around Nakhchivan in 1225-1226, the Khwarazmshah army temporarily established control over the region. The attitude of the local population played a significant role in shaping the course of these campaigns.

Due to its strategic location, economic potential, and proximity to major trade routes, Nakhchivan constituted an important stronghold for the Khwarazmians. In administering the territory, Jalal al-Din applied classical military-feudal methods. The presence of the Khwarazmshah army in Nakhchivan led to increased control of local administration by foreign military forces. In 1226-1227, heavy taxes were imposed in the region, and food supplies and livestock were requisitioned to meet the needs of the army. This policy placed a considerable economic and social burden on the local population. In sha'ban 624 AH (july-august 1227), Hajib Ali led a campaign into Azerbaijan and captured the city of Khoy. According to al-Nasawi, after taking Khoy, its surrounding fortresses, and Marand, he advanced toward Nakhchivan, which surrendered to him without resistance (11, p. 270; 1, p. 56). Ibn al-Athir likewise reports that the inhabitants of Nakhchivan voluntarily surrendered the city to Hajib Husam al-Din Ali, noting that had he wished to continue, he could have conquered the entire country (8, p. 199; 5, p. 55-56). Initially perceived as a defensive force against the Mongols, Jalal al-Din's system of governance soon generated widespread dissatisfaction. The voluntary surrender of Nakhchivan's population to Hajib Ali clearly demonstrates the local population's discontent with the harsh policies of the Khwarazmians.

In the final years of his rule, a certain moderation can be observed in Jalal al-Din Khwarazmshah's policies. Prolonged warfare had reduced the population to impoverishment. Taking into account the dire conditions of the population around Tabriz, Jalal al-Din ordered the distribution of food supplies from state granaries. In addition, the inhabitants of Tabriz were exempted from taxation for a period of three years (6, p. 95).

Nevertheless, the persistence of the Mongol threat and the growing dissatisfaction among the local population weakened Jalal al-Din's position. From 1229-

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